

THE PROBLEM OF STUDENTS' SELF-EDUCATION IN THE SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: This article examines the problem of self-education of schoolchildren in the process of educational work. The author draws attention to the particularly important role of self-education in the development of a child's personality. Reveals the forms and features of the work of teachers, gives advice and practical recommendations.

Key words: school, educational process, schoolchildren, self-education, pedagogical influence.

Introduction. The modern school is going through a difficult period, when a decisive turn is being made in the pedagogical process towards the student's personality. The new school must respect the dignity of each student, his individual needs and interests, and create favorable conditions for self-knowledge, self-development, self-determination and self-realization of the student's personality [1, 3, 7].

The ways of personal growth of students were considered by many scientists, teachers and psychologists, including B.G. Ananyev, Y. Aret, L.I. Bozhovich, O.I. Kochetov, A.G. Kovalev, O.M. Leontyev, S.L. Rubinstein, L. Ruvinsky.

Personality is formed under the influence of both external and internal factors [2, 4].

Internal factors of effective self-education include:

- formed and conscious self-knowledge and self-esteem;
- a sufficient level of self-awareness so that on its basis a person has a certain attitude towards the surrounding reality;

- organization of conflict between old and new aspirations of the individual. In the absence of experiencing such a conflict, the incentive to self-education will be ineffective;

- the formation of independence, which is expressed in the fact that a person, guided by his own needs, capabilities and interests, independently begins to determine the plan for his future life. Scientists note that making a decision to engage in self-education is feasible for a person, provided that he has experience in solving at least simple issues, life tasks facing him, the individual's need for accelerated development;

- a person's ability to self-govern, the presence of a developed will as a process of active conscious self-regulation.

A. G. Kovalev, A. A. Bodalev note the possibility of self-education among weak-willed people, but it is fickle, and they often differ only in good intentions [5, 6].

So, self-education is the internal formation of a person, the ascending component of which is self-development, enhanced by self-determination, self-attitude, self-affirmation [8, 9, 11]. It occurs only when a person sets a specific goal of self-development, self-improvement and strives to achieve it regardless of the situation in which he finds himself, using all favorable conditions and means for this. The external conditions for self-education are the following:

- systematic educational work;
- creating conditions for the comprehensive development of the individual;
- development of all forms of children's self-government. Increased independence and activity in the lives of students, encouraging children to be creative, as a result of which the skills and abilities of self-education are formed [10];
- comprehension of the life experience of adolescents, the development of public opinion, which is crucial for the formation of self-esteem, self-demandingness, for the formation of goals and objectives of self-education;

- consistency and direction of educational influence, as a result of which the relationship between educators and pets is regulated.

This is especially important for coordinating objective and subjective factors in the self-education of adolescents [12, 13].

Depending on what is the subject of self-education, three main forms can be distinguished in the psychological structure of the individual:

- the formation of a new mental formation in the individual, which has not existed before;
- self-transformation, breaking old stereotypes, habits, restructuring, restructuring or destroying them in oneself. A person overestimates his ideals and overcomes spontaneous tendencies in them. The author notes that the first and second forms are a search for oneself; they do not always end in the implementation of the main plan, despite the efforts;
- support for the integrity and stability of one's "I." Such self-education is aimed at the psychological preservation of the individual, to resist external influences and remain oneself. The success of self-education is determined by its stable motivation. Self-education motives are called "conscious reasons, interests, aspirations, attitudes, needs that force a person to work on himself" [14, 16].

A. Ya. Aret believes that the prerequisite for the emergence of a motive for self-education is "a certain level of development of consciousness and self-awareness of the individual, on the basis of which a person creates a certain attitude to reality, awareness of the relationship between "I" and "not-I", the relationship "I and the world" , "me and life".

The motive for self-education usually arises as a result of awareness of the degree of discrepancy between the "self-real" and the "ideal self" of the individual. Consequently, the motives for self-education are as follows:

- awareness by the individual of the need to overcome the gap between one's own capabilities and the demands of life. Understanding of this need arises when a person

sets certain tasks for himself; they can be determined by the characteristics of work and relationships with others [14, 15].

- Competition: the desire to be better than another, to be first, the development of the quality of an ideal stimulates the development of positive qualities in oneself and the eradication of negative qualities.
- Criticism from parents and other people surrounding the individual encourages him to self-analysis, awareness of his shortcomings, and the desire to change for the better [16, 18].
- An example of people around who are authorities, as well as the desire to become an example for others [17].
- The desire to coordinate one's own goals that meet the personal interests of the individual with the goals set by the team.
- The desire to acquire the necessary qualities to achieve success in a certain type of activity or future profession.
- The desire for success.
- Interests. If schoolchildren are interested in doing a certain type of activity, they will do it without control and coercion from their elders.
- The desire to cope with the task.

An important issue for guiding the self-education of schoolchildren is determining the sensitive period for this type of activity.

Even at primary school age, children are able to characterize the degree and expression of their own moral qualities, establish connections between the actions of other people and the qualities of their personality, and begin to analyze their behavior. But due to the lack of awareness of one's own personal qualities and the lack of formation of a certain attitude towards them, the child does not yet strive for self-education [18].

In early adolescence, students develop an interest in the inner world of a person, they strive to understand the characteristics of other people and themselves. The majority of self-education is focused on motives and interests, which are often

impulsive, unreasonable and situational. The older teenagers are, the stronger the influence of self-education on their psychological and practical preparation for future life.

The behavior of older adolescents clearly indicates the superiority of life views associated with an idea of the future. The role of characteristics that teach students to self-analysis is increasing, giving the teacher rich material for working with them [17].

In the process of organizing self-education, students are taught special techniques for working on themselves, which include:

- 1) Self-persuasion - consists of inviting the student to find arguments in a certain situation and, with their help, become convinced of the correctness or incorrectness of his action, or in a conflict situation, switch his thoughts to other topics and matters that would distract him from the conflict and calm him down;
- 2) Self-hypnosis - they suggest using it if necessary to overcome fear of difficulties, self-doubt, and indecision. Self-hypnosis involves the student repeating certain judgments mentally or out loud. For example, to overcome hot temper, you can offer the following judgment: "I hate my temper. I must and can get rid of it";
- 3) Self-encouragement. This technique is effective if the student is lost in difficult situations, despairs of his own strengths and capabilities;
- 4) Self-encouragement. It is used if the student, overcoming certain difficulties, has completed a complex task. It is effective when necessary to overcome negative personality traits;
- 5) Self-coercion. Helps in the fight against internal disorganization, reluctance to study, work, and laziness;
- 6) Self-analysis. It plays a decisive role in self-education, since it presupposes the ability to analyze one's actions and give them a certain assessment;
- 7) Practical techniques. These include the "step forward" technique - daily planning of activities for the next day; the "evaluation of the day" technique - the student's analysis of his actions, deeds, and shortcomings;

8) “Rules of my behavior.” Consists of following the rules of conduct drawn up for the student. Trains you to perform your duties;

9) Self-commitment. Provides for the student to plan work on himself for a month, semester or year, depending on what personality traits and in what time frame he seeks to form or overcome;

10) “Know yourself.” It has the nature of a game in which the teacher gives an incomplete description of the student without mentioning his last name. He recognizes himself, and his comrades complement this characteristic;

11) “Self-characterization” and “mutual characterization.” The essence of these techniques is to discuss the characteristic features of self-education in a group prepared in this way.

The ability to self-regulate is also important. Self-regulation of behavior is the ability to overcome obstacles along the way and be able to resist them.

Conclusions. So, self-education is one of the forms of self-improvement, which comes down to the child’s conscious development of his own positive qualities and the eradication of negative ones, and comparing oneself with the ideal and others helps determine which personality traits suit the child, which he will struggle with, and which ones he will still strive.

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